

**BIOECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
AGASTACHE FOENICULUM****Sarsenbaeva Z.
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19706755>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 18th April 2026Accepted: 20th April 2026Online: 22nd April 2026**KEYWORDS***Agastache foeniculum,
bioecological characteristics,
distribution, medicinal properties***ABSTRACT***The bioecological characteristics of anise hyssop
(Agastache foeniculum) are presented.*

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 26, 2020, No. PQ-4901, entitled “Measures to expand the scope of scientific research on the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants and the establishment of their seed production”, practical measures are being implemented to develop the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants, as well as to establish their seed production system [1].

Furthermore, in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 20, 2022, No. PQ-251, it is stated that decisions were adopted on the following: the organization of the cultivation of medicinal plants under cultural conditions, their processing, and the wide-scale utilization of these plants [2].

The protection of medicinal plants and their rational use is considered one of the most important issues of the present day. Currently, among the plants used in traditional medicine, the majority are either limited in number or are on the verge of extinction. Uzbekistan is very rich in plant genetic resources, with approximately 4,300 species of higher plants recorded. In traditional medicine, medicinal plants serve as the primary source for the treatment and prevention of diseases [5,6].

Anise hyssop (*Agastache foeniculum*) belongs to the Lamiaceae family and is a perennial plant. At present, it holds significant importance in the food industry, essential oil production, and medicine. Anise hyssop (*Agastache foeniculum*) is distinguished from other aromatic plants by its heat tolerance and its specific requirements for moisture [3,7].

Anise hyssop (*Agastache foeniculum*) is a perennial, heat-loving plant that grows to a height of 70–150 cm. Its stem is angular, and the leaves are arranged oppositely along the stem. The leaves are elongated-oval in shape, with slightly serrated margins. Their length ranges from 8 to 12 cm, and their width is approximately 4–5 cm.

The flowers are bisexual, small, and bluish-violet in color. They are arranged in dense inflorescences (spikes) up to 20 cm long, located at the top of the main and lateral stems. Each spike may contain more than 300–400 flowers.

The fruit is smooth, dark brown in color, and elongated in shape. All parts of anise hyssop contain about 0.5% essential oils, as well as flavonoids, antioxidants, approximately 0.005% ascorbic acid, and organic acids such as citric and malic acids [2,3,6].

Species of anise hyssop (*Agastache foeniculum*) are found in Siberia, Central Asia, as well as in northern and western regions, and in the Far East. In recent years, the plant has also spread across Southern European countries. It is cultivated in the southern regions of the United States and Russia. Under natural conditions, it is also found in North and Central America [3].

In Karakalpakstan, in recent years, specialized organizations have been actively engaged in the cultivation of medicinal plants. Scientific research on medicinal plants is being carried out in various research institutes. In particular, the biotechnology of cultivating anise hyssop under greenhouse conditions is currently being studied.

Anise hyssop (*Agastache foeniculum*) is considered to be very rich in medicinal properties. It is used in the treatment of diseases such as atherosclerosis, angina, prostatitis, hypertension, respiratory conditions, gastritis, and liver diseases. It also improves digestion, supports gastrointestinal function, helps detoxify the body, and slows down the aging process.

At present, it is also used in the treatment of hepatitis, which is relatively common among the population. When included in the daily diet—for example, in salads or combined with fish and meat products—it provides a pleasant aroma and is considered highly beneficial for health [3,4,7].

References:

1. Ózbekstan Respublikası Prezidentiniń 2020-jil 26-noyabrdegi «Dárilik ósimliklerdi jetistiriw hám qayta islew, olardıń tuqıngershiligin jolǵa qoyıwdı rawajlandırıw boyınsha ilimiy izertlew kólemin keńeytiwge baylanıslı ilajlar» haqqındaǵı PQ-4901 qararı. (Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 26, 2020, No. PQ-4901, “On measures to expand the scope of scientific research on the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants and the establishment of their seed production”).
2. Ózbekistan Respublikası Prezidentiniń 2022-jil 20-maydaǵı qabil etilgen, PQ 251-sanlı qararı (Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 20, 2022, No. PQ-251).
3. Faxriddinova, D. Lamiaceae oilasi ayrim turlarining morfo-biologik ko'rsatkichlari (Morpho-biological characteristics of some species of the Lamiaceae family). *Agro Ilm Journal*, 2023, No. 6, pp. 30–31.
4. Kozak, M.F., Turdugulova, R.T. Кариологическая характеристика лопанта анисового (*Lofanthus anisatus* Boenth.). (Karyological characteristics of anise hyssop). *Natural Sciences. Genetics*, No. 2(43), 2013, pp. 86–97.
5. Mashanov, V.I., Pokravskiy, A.A. Приано-ароматические растения. Лопант анисовый (многоколосник фенхельный) Ст-174-176. (Spice-aromatic plants. Anise hyssop). pp. 174–176.
6. Elmuratovna, T.S. Tırnaqúl ósimliginiń biologiyalıq hám dárilik qásiyeti. (Biological and medicinal properties of the Tyrnaqqúl plant). In: “Janubiy Orol boyi tabiiy resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish” (Rational Use of Natural Resources of the Southern Aral Region), 2021, p. 132.

7. Elmuratovna, T.S. Chakanda o'simligining dorivor xususiyatlari (Medicinal properties of the Chakanda plant). In: "Ilmiy tajiriybeler natijelerin awl xojaliginda qollanwda kadrlardin roli" (The Role of Personnel in Applying Scientific Results in Agriculture), 2019, pp. 72–73.

